

Management

THE INTERRELATION OF MAGISTRACY LEARNING MOTIVES AND STUDENTS' PERSONAL FEATURES

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Abstract

Psychologic features of learning activities' motives have paramount importance for the process of mastering a profession and they're a guarantee of professional's personal development. The problem of learning motivation is analyzed and is actively researched by specialists in the educational psychology, pedagogical psychology and professional activity's psychology. The goal of our research was to find out interrelation of motives of taking a master's degree and personal features of students. The study was conducted with the 1st and 2nd year students of master's program of Public Administration Academy of Republic Armenia. During the research we used the method of testing. We used Cattell personality inventory and method of studying the student's motivation. 30 students of master's programs, whose personal qualities were studied in 2014 (at the beginning of their studying for master's degree) by the Cattell's test, took part in the study. The motivation of training activity was researched with the method of studying student's motivation during the tuition in 2015, by the time, when first year of master's program was ending. We've provided correlational analysis, because the goal of our research was to find out relations of motivation of training activity and personal features.

The generalization of theoretical and experimental information shows that motivation of training activity of a person is provided by personal factors. Accounting of personal factors will give a chance to increase motivation of learning activity in the process of realization of educational programs. Accordingly it'll help to prepare qualified professionals, who will fit the needs of modern society.

Keywords: Motives; Independence; Personal Features; Training Activity; Magistracy; Profession; Psychological Analysis.

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1. Introduction

K. Pounds in book "The psychology of Management" shows a great idea Different ways on different days [5]. It means that education system for the modern society have to prepare specialists

in different way. The best educational programs can't prepare qualified specialists, if a student isn't enough motivated to learn a profession and he doesn't see prospects to find a job. Modern pedagogical approaches focus on perfection of different learning methods, which are directed at forming interest to profession in teachers. These approaches provide training programs, which focus on forming adequate professional thinking and skills of solving problems in different professional situations. We should note the fact, that learning educational subjects from the perspective of pedagogics assumes acquirement of professional knowledge, skills and abilities, but from the perspective of psychology it assumes complete demonstration of personality in profession. Wherein, different needs of a person, which may sometimes differ from a study and professional goals, should be satisfied. It's known, that while choosing profession, one is lead not only by the need of self-actualization, but also by various demonstrations of the whole motivational sphere's hierarchy. Attitude to profession and satisfaction by that emphasize the fact how much a person is motivated in their development in that profession. Consequently, it should be noted, that motives of profession learning are caused not only by pedagogical approaches, but also those personal features of training activity subject, which guide a personality to satisfy the needs in training activity. Studies show, that actuality of solving the problem of training activity motivation is directly connected to specific parameters of learning process' efficiency. It's known that negative or indifferent attitude to learning may be the cause of student's slow or poor progress. It's noted, that timely diagnostics and correction of learning motivation, as the basis of solving the motivation problem, is an urgent problem of psychologists [4].

A.P. Chernyavskaya notes that students' formation to training activity subjects is impossible without the development of appropriate motivation. The author thinks that the problem of development of training activity motivation isn't new one, but it becomes actual again with the introduction of new learning standards, based on systematic-activity, competence and variable approaches. Both the development of competencies and the need to make a choice (content, time, forms and methods of learning) are impossible, if students won't act purposefully, actively and responsibly in learning process. Exactly, motives perform goal-making and point-making functions in activity [9].

It should be noted, that author considers learning motivation in student age as a new standard of teaching.

The problem of learning motivation is analyzed and is actively researched by specialists in the educational psychology, pedagogical psychology and professional activity's psychology. Some of them note that learning motivation is a special case of motivation, which is a very important part of learning process. Learning motivation is caused by some interrelated factors: system of education and institutions, organizations of educational process and also subjective features of a teacher [14]. The specific of academic subject has a great role. Some authors, basing on numerous studies' results, state, that in learning process in the university, students' leading motives for studying are both professional and learning motives. According to this, person's motivation is modified in two directions: the content and the qualitative characteristics of motives change. Personal-activity approach, proposed by I.A Zimnyaya, promotes forming motives of training activity in students most of all. A. V. Smirnova considers that training activity's motives may be formed by evaluation and specially organized independent work. The ability to show independence and initiative in learning is a necessary condition for creating an interest to content of learning in

students. The more active learning methods are, the easier to make students interested [8]. In our perspective, the role of self-dependence grows in magistracy, because master's degree is gained by those people, who already found their professional way.

2. Research Methods and Materials

There are training activity's studies of student age in scientific literature, which include only the studies of students, who have only a bachelor's degree. R.S Weisman (1973), researching the dynamics of changing motives of creative achievement of all the bachelor classes' students-psychologists, emphasized motives of "formal-academic" achievement and "achievement needs". Telling about creative achievement, the author means aspiration to solving any scientific or technical problem and aspiration to the success in scientific activity. "Formal-academic" achievement's motif is considered as a motivation to high level progress. "Achievement need" is interpreted as a bright intensity that and other motif. R.S Weisman found, that motif of creative achievement and achievement need increase on senior students of bachelor, while "formal-academic" achievement, instead, decrease from 2nd to 3-4th year [2].

The goal of our research was to find out interrelation of motives of taking a master's degree and personal features of students. The study was conducted with the 1st and 2nd year students of master's program of Public Administration Academy of Republic Armenia.

During the research we used the method of testing. We used Cattell personality inventory and method of studying the student's motivation. 30 students of master's programs, whose personal qualities were studied in 2014 (at the beginning of their studying for master's degree) by the Cattell's test, took part in the study. The motivation of training activity was researched with the method of studying student's motivation during the tuition in 2015, by the time, when first year of master's program was ending. This method has three scales: obtaining knowledge, mastering the profession, obtaining a diploma. Obtaining knowledge marks student's aspiration to get knowledge, i.e. student's curiosity. Mastering the profession shows the acquisition of professional knowledge and professionally important qualities. The scale of obtaining a diploma indicates formal mastering the knowledge [6].

3. Results

The analysis of the results of Cattell's test's index dynamics showed, that the average index of master's students' independence has average level of severity $x = 4.23$, see table 1. Table 1 shows average indexes of independence of master's students according to academic year. Master's students have the index of independence, equal to 4.4 or 4.1 points, while the maximum in this scale is 9-12 points.

4. The Discussion of the Results

In the works of L.I. Bojovich it's emphasized, that holistic structure of a personality is determined by its direction, at first. Steady dominating system of motives, which arises during the life and education, is a basis of a person's directionality. Wherein, the basic and leading motives of that system characterize the structure of person's motivational sphere, subjecting all others [1, p.21].

In the works of E. P. Ilyin it's also viewed different approaches of motivation. He especially emphasizes learning motivation. According to the author, learning motivation is all the factors, which determine training activity: needs, goals, settings, sense of duty, interests, etc. [2].

Psychological studies of training activity's motivation are mainly related to school age, while the student age is studied very little. The most researched directions in this area are motives of going to university (Bobrovickaya S.V., Pechnikov A.N. Muchina G.A., Vovchik-Blakitnaya M.V. et al.), dynamics of motives' changing during the learning process in the university (Weisman R.S. Gebos A.I. et al.), students' attitude to different academic subjects (Rean A.A., Yakunin V.A., Meshkov N.I. et al.) [3].

Motivation is considered as a component of psychological structure of activity and is successfully studied on the basis of principles of systemic genetic approach. (Y.P. Vavilov, Y.P. Povarenkov, A.A. Rean, V.D Shadrikov, V.A. Yakunin). According to this approach motivation acts as a complex system of psychic processes, where different elements and their relations are distinguished [4].

We reckon that motivation of student's training activity is a complex education, which includes personal psychological factors of a student, person's system of values, and, of course, education programs.

The maturity of the personality is assessed by the level of the formation of valuable orientations. Their underdevelopment and inconsistency is a sign of psychic infantilism, which breeds impulsivity and non-adequacy of behavior. So, person's values and motives form life strategy and determine the way of professional development [13].

A.I. Gebos developed factors of student's positive motives to learning. He emphasized some factors, which appears as contributing conditions for students' training activity. According to the author, the factors are awareness of the immediate and ultimate goals; awareness of theoretical and practical significance of assimilating knowledge; emotional form of academic material's statement; show of "prospective lines " in development of scientific concepts; professional directionality of training activity; choosing tasks, which create problematic situations in the structure of learning activity; availability of curiosity and " informative psychological climate in learning group" [2].

Some of these conditions are used in the basis of creating educational programs in modern pedagogical approaches, but there are others, which relate to professional skills of a teacher.

Some psychologists, studying students' motivation, rely on inner motives and consider, that student should have a wish to learn. The students' motivation relates to the wish of students to take part in learning process. But it also relates to causes and goals, which are lying in the heart of students' participation in scientific activity [15, 16]. Despite the fact, that students may be equally motivated for solving the problem, the sources of their motivation may be different. Learning causes sense of duty for a student, who is motivated to take a responsibility for their wellbeing (Mark Lepper 1988). Externally motivated student performs "for getting some prize or to avoid

punishment, which is external to that activity”, such as likes, stickers or the approval of teachers (Lepper) [12].

Herzberg states, that a man works more efficiently in the case, if the work is a happiness and not punishment for him. The worker, who is interested in his job, isn't so demanding for the salary and other external factors, so his activity is much more efficient. Herzberg considers that work should be interesting for a man. He stands for man's happiness and call managers to make work happy and interesting for the work to be more productive, opening reserves, which are held in the people. He thinks that, working processes should be reconstructed and the workers should rule their job [7].

In our perspective it relates to learning motivation, student should be interested in learning processes, it has to bring satisfaction. At the same time, studying should be interesting and saturated.

The analysis of scientific literature let us to conclude that motives of training activity are driven by several factors. We reckon that personal features of a student have the decisive role and importance among these factors. Motives of profession choice and motives of professional development sometimes differ due to the essence of the profession and due to public image of that profession [16]. It's considered that motives of people, who choose managing profession, differ from motives for other professions.

The information about relations of motivation and personal qualities are shown in table2.

We've provided correlational analysis, because the goal of our research was to find out relations of motivation of training activity and personal features. Negative correlation is found between sociability and knowledge obtainment $r = -0.52$. Consequently, the more master's students are sociable, are able to provide interpersonal contacts, prefer work with people and social approval, like to be modern, the more motivation of obtaining knowledge decreases. On the other hand, if they're unsociable, prefer to work, when they're isolated, the motivation of training activity increases. There are proves for that sociable people may be leaders in small groups and very often choose the work with people, while unsociable people may be painters, scientists and prefer to work independently, when they're isolated from the group.

Negative correlation is found between dominance and obtainment of a profession $r = -0.36$. It's known that if one has high scores of dominance, the person is characterized by the following qualities: self-dependence, independence, perseverance, persistency, perversity, sometimes aggression, refusal of recognition external power, addiction to authoritarian behavior, thirst for admiration. From correlation we may conclude that the more such qualities person has, the less he will aim to master the profession. It's assumed, that dominancy and perversity aren't connected to professional skills.

Negative correlation is also found between mastering the profession and suspicion $r = -0.54$. Cattell called that factor alaxia-protensia. This term stands as protection and sometimes reflects as internal tension. Accordingly high scores of this factor may be provided by person's neurotic characteristics. It should be noted, that high scores of this factor are often met among people with

independent behavior and people, whose work is connected with creation of something, for instance, in the area of religion and science. Some characteristics of a person, which relate to dominance (factor E), in fact should be connected to this factor. Low score of this factor characterizes an open, kind person without ambitions and aim to win. From all of this we may consider, that if a person is suspicious, mistrustful, stubborn, works badly in a group, cares for others very little, and then the person's motivation of mastering the profession decreases.

Negative correlation is found between motivation of obtaining knowledge and tension $r = -0.42$. Such connection marks that, the more a person aims to obtain knowledge, the more he satisfies by the things he has. Consequently the level of achievement motivation decreases, excessive satisfaction manifests.

Negative correlation is also found between getting a diploma and radicalism $r = -0.43$. We may conclude from this, that the more master's students are disposed to experiments, receptive for changes, new ideas, directed to analytic and theoretical activity, the less motivation of getting a diploma they have. It means, that free-thinking person can't formally get knowledge, which is equal to aiming just get a diploma.

Negative correlation is found between motivation of obtaining knowledge and normativity of behavior $r = -0.38$. Therefore, with the high motivation of getting knowledge person may refuse to carry our requirements and norms of the group, may wink disorganization, irresponsibility, flexibility to other social norms.

Viewing positive correlations, we should note, that such connection is found between courage and motivation of getting knowledge $r = 0.39$. By the Cattell's test courage is a definite factor, which characterizes the level of activity in social contacts. This factor has genetic origin and shows activity of an organism and temperament's features. High scores of this factor talks about that person is intended to risky acts. For such people it's true to type to be persistent, they can withstand emotional loads, which often makes them leaders. In learning activity this factor helps in obtaining knowledge. Low scores of this factor characterize timid, shy and unsociable people, for whom it's very hard to make decisions. Accordingly, we may conclude, that if the one is enterprising, active, ready for risk, independent, may make unordinary decisions, then they are more intended to getting knowledge.

Positive correlation is found between mastering the profession and self-control $r = 0.35$. Such connection may talk about that the more a person seeks to get professional important qualities, master the profession, the more he shows purposefulness, strong will, ability to control emotions and behavior.

Interesting connection is found between getting a diploma and sociability $r = 0.40$, which talks about that the more one seeks to formally get knowledge, the more he is sociable in interpersonal contacts, natural, ready to cooperating, to group work, inclined to empathy, sympathy, and understanding other people (correlation between obtaining a diploma and sensitivity $r = 0.54$).

5. Conclusions

So, summing theoretical and experimental information, we see that motivation of training activity of a person is provided by personal factors. Accounting of personal factors will give a chance to increase motivation of learning activity in the process of realization of educational programs. Accordingly it'll help to prepare qualified professionals, who will fit the needs of modern society.

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